

Home Environment and Social Adjustment of Secondary School Students: A Study in Kashmir

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Abstract:- The milieu in which a child develops physically, intellectually, emotionally, culturally, and socially is his or her home. A child's entire growth is influenced by his or her family environment. The data for this descriptive research was collected from 300 secondary school students using self-constructed questionnaires. Statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation, percentage method, t-test, and Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation were employed to investigate the acquired data. This study discovered a significant association between home environment and social adjustment of secondary school students of Kashmir. The data also revealed that when it comes to the home environment and social adjustment, male and female secondary school students had significantly different mean scores. When students were assessed based on their geographic location (urban vs rural), it was evident that rural secondary school students had better home contexts and social adaptations than their urban counterparts. Because the home environment has such a considerable impact on students' social adjustment, it is highly encouraged that they are provided with peace and tranquility at home so that, through valiant efforts, sheer determination, and familial support, they can achieve all of their career ambitions and acclimate well to the society in which they live.

Keywords:- Home Environment, Social Adjustment, Secondary School Students, Peace, Valiant efforts, Familial support.

I. INTRODUCTION

“The strength of a nation derives from the integrity of the home” – Confucius

Man is a social being, for one reason or the other he is dependent on people in the society. He has to fit himself according to the rules, norms, mores, customs, traditions, and culture of the society. Adjustment is when equilibrium is maintained between a person and his environment. Many factors determine social adjustment of a person which includes socio-economic factors, good work habits, interpersonal relationship skills, emotional control, family cohesion, home environment and nature of family relations. Greater social maturity is required as the child learns to adjust to social situations. Social adjustment refers to what extent a child shows acceptability in his relationship with other children and adults. Home environment has a significant impact on adjustment behavior and overall development of a child. Home environment refers to the mutual respect and interaction among the members of a family. Each and every factor linked with home like

qualification status of parents, cooperation between members, social and financial status, nature and size of family etc. greatly influences a child. Both negative and positive conditions represent the total home environment, in which the mutual interaction is either supportive or discouraging to decide home environment to be poor or better. Tijani (2017) in his research study concluded that students from ideal homes show better academic performance as compared to the students from un-ideal homes. This result is also supported by the study of Egunsola (2014), by arguing that each factor linked with home are strongly correlated and have significant impact on academic performance of secondary school students in agricultural science. The congenial environment of both home and school greatly enables the students to excel in their respective fields and helps in the inculcation and awareness of civic responsibilities (Pingle, 2015). Due to variation in the home factors children perform differently when taught under same learning situations (Adeyemi, 2018). Sharma and Bandhana (2012) in their research study, “A study of home environment and reasoning ability among secondary school students” revealed that reasoning ability is strongly affected by home environment. Higher level of reasoning ability was shown by the students with high home environment when compared with students with low home environment. Naik and Dubey (2018) also revealed in their research that on academic achievement of tribal region secondary school students the interactional effect of home environment is significant. Gosain (2019) analyzed that academic anxiety is caused by the authoritative home environment where as the same is reduced by caring and friendly home environment. The result is also supported by the study conducted by Kumar (2013). The adjustment of students to discipline is significantly related to home social relations, which means that when parents show warmth, care and love to their children, their life will be positively affected and they will manifest disciplined behavior (Sakirudeen, 2017). Gender based differences exist in adjustment. Males are better adjusted as compared to females and social support has positive but insignificant relation with adjustment. A reasonable compromise should be achieved by an individual between the demands of society and his drive for self-realization (Srivastava & Barmola, 2012). The results on gender bases are contradicted by the findings of research conducted by Manikandan and Selvaraju (2017) where they asserted that in comparison to their counterparts' female students are better in adjustment dimensions. A research study undertaken by Kavand and Jansari “Social adjustment of students' residing in hostel and at home” revealed that in comparison to students residing in hostels, students at home are better adjusted. This

indicates that home environment has a direct impact on the adjustment of students.

The review analysis leads to the conclusions that home environmental conditions affect many aspects of students whether their academic, personal or social life is concerned. Various studies conducted so far have proven the results. Gosain(2019) explored the significant relation between home environment and academic anxiety. Between anxiety and adjustment significant relationship was found by Manikandan and Selvaraju(2017). Home environment has significant impact on academic achievement of secondary school students (Dubey & Naik,2018). Kavadi and Jansari (2019) allowed the discussion that home environment plays a significant role in the social adjustment of students when compared with students at hostel. Similarly, Nisarga and Nambiar (2020) examined the relationship between home environment and self-esteem and was found to be significant.

II. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Home is the first school of a child and a miniature society. Home environment good or poor greatly affects the Childs' brain development, learning, discipline, school, social and emotional adjustment & his overall development. A child imitates the behavior patterns of the family members at home. The type and nature of home environment, ways adopted by the parents for nurturing influences and motivates the child accordingly. Pappu(2017) in his study agrees that not only by the efforts of child itself, the efforts of his parents and the home environment in which child is brought up are also responsible for his success, as good education depends on these factors, it does not come by chance. The present study will explore the importance of providing good home environment to students which in turn will help them to be responsible members of their society and adjust in accordance to its existing norms, excel in their studies and achieve success.

A. Objectives

- To study the home environment of secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To study the social adjustment of secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To compare the home environment of male and female secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To compare the home environment of rural and urban secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To compare the social adjustment of male and female secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To compare the social adjustment of rural and urban secondary school students of Kashmir.
- To study the relation between home environment and social adjustment of secondary school students of Kashmir

B. Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students on home environment.
- There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students on home environment
- There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students on social adjustment
- There is no significant difference between rural and urban secondary school students on social adjustment.
- There is no relationship between home environment and social adjustment of secondary school students of Kashmir.

III. OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

A. Home environment

In this study home environment refers to all those factors (care, love, acceptance, rejection, isolation, mutual connection, respect, encouragement, permissiveness, strictness, reward, punishment, conflict, moral support, physical facilities), linked with home whether positive or negative which on working together make conditions at home for child either favorable or unfavorable.

B. Social adjustment

Social adjustment in this study refers to the behavior of a child in accordance with or against the existing social rules and regulations (social interaction, culture cooperation, docility, rebelliousness, violation, helpfulness, integration).

C. Secondary school students

Secondary school students in present study refers to all those students who are studying in 9th, 10th, 11th & 12th classes indifferent higher secondary schools in Kashmir.

IV. SAMPLE AND METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted to analyze the home environment and social adjustment of secondary school students of Kashmir. The study is descriptive in nature and self-constructed questionnaires both for home environment and social adjustment were used consisting of 20 statements each, and against each statement a 5 point Likert scale was given (Always, Mostly, Normally, Sometimes, Never) and used to collect the relevant information from the sample subjects and for the same Google Forms were sent to them via WhatsApp messages to conduct the descriptive online survey and respondents were assured regarding the confidentiality of their responses. A total of 300 secondary school students from classes 9th, 10th, 11th & 12th classes were sampled for this study.

A. Statistical Treatment

To analyze and interpret the data collected from the sample subjects, Percentage method, mean, Standard Deviation, t-test and Karl Pearson's Coefficient of Correlation were used.

B. Analysis and Interpretation

a) Home Environment.

	Mean	Standard deviation	Range of scores	Type and percentage of students
Home Environment (H.E*)	50.05	11.00	27- 83	Poor H.E = 36% Average H.E= 48% Good H.E = 16%

Table 1

It is clearly evident from the results that 36% of sampled secondary school students revealed that they are living in poor home environmental conditions, while as good number of students i.e., 48% are being provided with

average home environmental conditions and only 16% secondary school students revealed that they perceive good home environmental conditions.

b) Social Adjustment

Social Adjustment (S.A*)	Mean	standard deviation	Range of scores	type and percentage of student
	47.34	10.61	20-90	Poor S.A = 44% Average S.A = 46.66% Good S.A = 9.34 %

Table 2

After data interpretation it was revealed that 44 % secondary school students were having poor social adjustments and 46.66% of students were with average

social adjustments, on the other hand only 9.34 % students showed good social adjustments.

Fig.1.1

Fig.2.1

c) Comparison on home environment between male and female secondary school students.

(H.E*)	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	52.8	13.7	2.07	0.05
Female	200	49.6	10.26		

Table 3

The calculated t-value came out to be 2.07 and is significant at 0.05 level of significance, therefore the above stated hypothesis 'There is no significant difference between

the home environment of male and female secondary school students' stands rejected, as the difference has been confirmed by the results.

d) Comparison between rural and urban secondary school students on home environment

(H.E)*	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	134	52.62	12	2.57	0.05
Urban	166	49.27	10.17		

Table: 4

The calculated t-value as shown above (in Table-4) 2.57 is significant at 0.05 level but is slightly lower than the tabulated t-value(2.59) at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis formulated as ‘There is no significant difference between urban and rural secondary

school students’ onhome environment’stands rejected. It is inferred from the above results that rural secondary school students have better home environments than their urban counterparts,

e) Comparison between male and female secondary school students on social adjustment.

(S.A*)	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Male	100	50.10	10.09	3.25	0.01
Female	200	46.55	9.97		

Table 5

The tabulated t-values at 298degrees of freedom for 0.01 and0.05 level of significance is2.59 and 1.97 respectively. Therefore, it is clearly evident from the above table that the calculated t- value is significant at 0.01 level of significance as revealed by the results. The formulated hypothesis‘There is no significant difference between male

and female secondary school students’ on social adjustments.’is therefore rejected and this result indicates that on social adjustments in comparison to female secondary school students’ males are socially better adjusted.

f) Comparison between rural and urban secondary school students on social adjustments.

(S.A*)	N	Mean	Standard deviation	t-value	Level of significance
Rural	134	48.58	9.09	2.12	0.05
Urban	166	46.18	10.72		

Table 6

The results as given in Table-6 indicates that the calculated t-value is significant at 0.05 significance level and it is therefore clear from the results that the null hypothesis stated as ‘There is no significant difference

between rural and urban secondary school students’ on social adjustments’is rejected here, as the difference between rural and urban secondary school students has been confirmed to be significant.

g) Home environment and Social Adjustment.

Pearson’s coefficient of correlation(r)	Calculated Value	Significance level
Home Environment and Social Adjustment	0.11	0.05

Table 7

The findings reveal that the effect is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. The tabulated t-value for Pearson’s Coefficient of Correlation(r) is 0.113 with 298 df (degrees of freedom) significant at 0.05 level of significance.It can be inferred from the results that between home environment and social adjustment correlation is

significant. Therefore, the hypothesis stated as, ‘There is no relationship between home environment and social adjustment of secondary school students’ of Kashmir.’ stands rejected.

V. MAJOR FINDINGS

The scores of total sample were distributed into three categories *Poor (20-45)*, *Average (46-60)* and *Good (above 61)* for both *home environment* and *social adjustment*. The mean score calculated for *home environment* was 50.05 which fall in the *average* level category, it is thus inferred from the results that the secondary school students in Kashmir had *average home environment*. Similarly, mean score for *social adjustment* of secondary school students was found to be 47.34 which also fall in the *average* level category and thus, this aspect of result revealed that the secondary school students showed *average social adjustments*.

- Significant difference between the home environment of male and female secondary school students has been found. The findings of this research confirmed that males having better home environment than their counterparts.
- It has been found that significant difference exists between home environment of rural and urban secondary school students. Rural students having good home environment as compared to urban students was confirmed by their mean difference.
- Significant difference between the social adjustment of male and female secondary school students was found. Males were found to be going good with social adjustments when compared with their female counterparts.
- The results reveal that between rural and urban secondary school students, on social adjustment, significant difference was found. It was found that rural students had good social adjustments in comparison to urban students.
- It has been found that between home environment and social adjustment there is statistically significant positive relationship

VI. CONCLUSION

Broadly translated our findings indicate that home environment has significant impact on social adjustment of secondary school students. Therefore, it is the duty of parents and other family members to provide better conditions to their children at home, as home environment being the major factor is linked to all other factors (like cultural, personal, social, emotional, academics etc.) of their life. It is therefore recommended that serenity and tranquility be provided to them at home so that with good efforts, hard work and parental support they can achieve all their targets in life and adjust themselves well in the society they live in. The interaction between family members should be respectful and cooperative so that it can have positive and good impression on the behavior of child, as it is said that children learn by imitation. It is the responsibility of parents to inculcate in their children the social values and qualities so that they are better adjusted to their society.

• Data Availability Statement

Data not available due to [ethical/legal/commercial] restrictions. Due to the nature of this research, participants of this study did not agree for their data to be shared publicly, so supporting data is not available.

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